

Proto-component signal transduction systems

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How cells and organisms communicate with each other is a fundamental question in biology. Gasoreceptors (such as O₂-sensing Dos) and riboreceptors can be considered examples of protein and ribonucleic acid-based one-component signal transduction systems.¹⁻⁶ Likewise, fructose-1P- and fructose-6P-sensing GKRP swodkoreceptor and also the potential O₂-sensing O₂ binding globin gasoreceptors can be considered as split-component signal transduction system.⁷⁻⁹ However, this raises the question: What about earlier evolutionary versions of these systems?⁶ Which came first? The allosteric site or the catalytic site of an enzyme?¹⁰ Regardless of the “evolutionarily correct” answer to this question, let’s focus on competitive inhibitors that can bind to such enzymes. Isn’t the “competitive inhibitor” that binds to the catalytic sites of these systems also a signaling molecule? And isn’t the absence of a signaling response upon its binding a signal in itself? (For example, if a traffic signal stops working, isn’t also a signal? Proceed with caution!) I propose the term “proto-component signal transduction system” to encompass all signaling mediated by competitive inhibitor binding. Finally, it is also worth considering other factors that bind to or alter the structure of such sites.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

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